

NBSINFRA

Funded by the
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City lab Booklet

Aveiro

Portugal

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All the City Labs

The **NBSINFRA** project has **five city labs across Europe** that are assessing **how cities can handle different challenges and stay resilient through Nature-Based Solutions**. Each city lab aims to investigate how NBS can protect local infrastructure, preserve biodiversity, restore ecosystems and confront the challenges of climate change. The goal is to deliver tailored solutions and risk indicators for specific locations, contribute to city contingency plans and **increase the resilience and sustainability of NBS for future generations**.

Nature Based Solutions stages across City labs

1	(Co-) Diagnosis and (Co-) Characterization Collaborative assessment of the current conditions and identification of key challenges and opportunities.
2	(Co-) Design and (Co-) Creation Co-designing and co-creating nature-based solutions with input from diverse stakeholders.
3	(Co-) Implementation Collaborative implementation of the solutions, ensuring active participation from all involved parties.
4	(Co-) Evaluation and (Co-) Monitoring Ongoing evaluation and monitoring of the solutions effectiveness through collective input and feedback.
5	(Co-) Amplification or (Co-) Replication Expanding or replicating the solutions collaboratively to ensure broader impact and scalability.

Ruse
Bulgaria

NBS stages: 1

Fingal
Ireland

NBS stages: 1-2

Aveiro
Portugal

NBS stages: 1-2

Prague
Czechia

NBS stages: 3-4

Cologne
Germany

NBS stages: 4

Visit our website for a more accurate insight on the project's city labs

www.nbsinfra.eu

Aveiro

Portugal

Historical/Cultural context

Ria de Aveiro, which receives different watersheds and rivers, forming one of the most notable wetlands of Portugal, and its entire natural heritage play an essential role in the identity and development of Aveiro.

During the Middle Ages, in the 10th and 11th centuries, Aveiro began forming around the Ria, driven by fishing, salt production and maritime activities. While traces of earlier settlements exist, urban growth accelerated after mass personal transport reshaped the city. From the mid-20th century onward, Aveiro experienced rapid growth, recording high growth rates. The urban sprawl expanded the boundaries of urbanization to a larger part of

the territory, often neglecting natural ecosystems. Settlements frequently turned away from their natural heritage, leading to increased soil impermeability, disrupted ecosystems, and exacerbated environmental challenges. These areas hold significant potential for future development, focusing on enhancing environmental quality and expanding public amenities to create a more balanced and sustainable urban landscape.

Diagnosis and Characterization of the case study

The City Lab focuses on the area surrounding Aveiro, aiming to understand the primary freshwater basin that feeds the urban canals crossing the city centre. The Categorization and Diagnosis of the case study involved several key analyses, which provided a comprehensive understanding of the watershed's dynamics, forming the foundation for developing NBS.

Hydraulic definition

This process mapped the watershed's boundaries, main and secondary watercourses, and urbanized areas along the riverbanks. Cartographic and land use analysis identified key structures and areas needing intervention.

Rainfall Analysis and Land Use

The rainfall analysis examined precipitation data and watershed permeability. Since 2001, the highest recorded rainfall was equivalent to 36 Olympic-sized pools in an hour. Land use trends over the past decade show significant urbanization, reducing agricultural areas and increasing impermeability, which affects water flow and heightens flood risks.

Hydrological study area:

Land use of case study:

Permeability of the case study:

Rainfall Analysis and Land Use

The watershed morphology was analyzed using topographic surveys and digital terrain modelling. The study revealed variations in riverbank positions over time, channel modifications, and bank erosion. The longitudinal profile showed areas of higher flow velocity and increased flood risk, particularly in flatter sections downstream.

Flood Flow Estimation

Hydrological modelling with HEC-HMS simulated basin behaviour using meteorological and geographical data. Statistical kinematic methods estimated flood flows of 18.2 m³/s for a 10-year return period and 28.6 m³/s for a 100-year return period. Additional topographic surveys improved model accuracy, refining watershed representation and enhancing flood predictions.

Hazards Analysis

The study area faces multiple hazards, some of which were increased due to altered flow patterns, upstream channelization, and failed stabilization efforts.

Multiple hazards:

Flooding risks

Riverbank erosion

Ecosystem degradation

Poor water quality

Landside risks

Deforestation

Species Mapping

Through regular field visits, species mapping was conducted using techniques such as photo-based species monitoring. This mapping provided valuable information, including the identification of invasive species and beneficial species relevant to the case study.

Entry into the Field

This stage was essential for presenting the initiative to the community, encouraging active participation, and integrating local knowledge, perspectives, and feedback from the very start into the project. The team engaged deeply with the community to map stakeholders, understand the local context, and address challenges, fostering trust, two-way communication, and a solid foundation for collaboration and co-production.

Our key principles for field entry and social engagement:

Communication

Transparency

Clarity

Trust

Inclusion

Our key approaches for mapping stakeholders:

Approaching key players

Meetings

Interviews

Walkthrough with locals

Direct observations

Long stays with the community

Informal talks, coffee, lunch, etc.

Capacity Building on NBS

Summer School

The Summer School promoted capacity building, community engagement, and collaboration through interactive activities, science communication, and expert-focused sessions like webinars and masterclasses, strengthening local involvement and the project's network. Key highlights included interactive exhibits, engaging games, design thinking using LEGO, demonstrations of real NBS, hands-on activities and more.

What's next?

The next stages of the project will focus on Co-Design and Co-Creation, featuring participatory activities like a story map on our website and in-person workshops.

Furthermore, we are committed to engaging with schools and vulnerable communities to ensure everyone's voice is heard.

Key activities

Completed activities

- Characterization of watershed
- Rainfall Analysis and Land Use
- Watershed morphology
- Hydrologic modeling
- Species Mapping
- Stakeholders Mapping
- Field entry
- Summer School

Future activities

- Co-creation workshops
- Territorial strategy definition
- Co-design of the most optimal NBS
- Setting expectations alignment

Best practices

The City Lab has learned many valuable lessons, and we hope that transforming these lessons into best practices will be useful for other projects, decision-makers, municipalities, experts, and practitioners worldwide, especially when faced with similar conditions.

Best practices for modelling the case study:

- Use trustworthy data
- Track the past history of the area
- One problem, many ways to solve it
- Always validate models

Best practices for Meaningful Engagement:

- Engage a variety of stakeholders
- Build trust and communicate clearly:
 - Take time to build personal relationships
- Collaborate with local authorities and stakeholders early on: keep communication open but expect bureaucratic delays
- Understand and respect the local context:
 - Respect local culture, engage leaders, and consider community perspectives and past experiences
- Plan and coordinate with local authorities
- Manage public expectations transparently:
 - Set realistic expectations and provide regular updates
- Stay present and engaged in the field:
 - Physical presence and informal conversations strengthens relationships
- Adapt and refine engagement strategies based on feedback
- Ensuring Inclusion of Vulnerable Populations:
 - Use participatory tools like story mapping to engage residents in their own environments
- Addressing misinformation and managing expectations: Maintain transparency to build trust and be prepared to address unrealistic expectations

NBSINFRA

“Nature-based Solutions address societal challenges through actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural and modified ecosystems, benefiting people and nature at the same time.

They target major challenges like climate change, disaster risk reduction, food and water security, biodiversity loss and human health, and are critical to sustainable development.”

International Union for Conservation of Nature

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www.nbsinfra.eu

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